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Digital Knowledge, Skills and Application among Librarians and Library Staff of MUNPARLAS Library Association, Incorporated

Objective. The study aimed to identify and assess a level of digital knowledge, a level of digital skills, and a level of digital application of the librarians and library staff who are members of MUNPARLAS Library Association, Inc. **Methods.** Descriptive-correlational research design was used in this study to provide static pictures of situations as well as to establish the relationship between different variables. The respondents of this study are 60 Librarians and Library Personnel who are members of MUNPARLAS Library Association, Inc. **Results.** Findings revealed that the respondents' level of digital knowledge was very high, with an average weighted mean of 3.39. The respondents' level of digital skills was also very high, with an average weighted mean of 3.25. Additionally, the respondents' level of digital application was very high, with an average weighted mean of 3.52. There was a significant relationship between the respondents' digital knowledge and digital skills, as indicated by a p-value of 0.000, which was lower than the Pearson r-value of 0.812. Similarly, there was a significant relationship between the respondents' digital skills and digital application, with a p-value of 0.000, lower than the Pearson r-value of 0.712. Lastly, there was also a significant relationship between the respondents' digital knowledge and digital application, with a p-value of 0.000, lower than the Pearson r-value of 0.649. Therefore, it is necessary to propose an action plan to sustain the digital knowledge, skills, and application among librarians and library staff at MLAI. **Conclusions.** The findings of this study underscore the importance of digital literacy in the field of librarianship. MLAI should continue to prioritize the cultivation of digital knowledge, skills, and application among its staff to adapt to the evolving needs of its users and to stay ahead in the digital age.

Keywords: digital knowledge; skills; librarians; library staff; library associations

Introduction

It is a generally accepted fact that this pandemic became the most unexpected event for every person around the globe. School face to face classes and all offices whether public or private changed most of their everyday routine on how to serve their clients. Abrupt use of digital platforms became mandatory particularly in the field of Education. Libraries on the other hand need to focus in delivering services online to support their communities. For this to be effective, librarians, including library staff, must have knowledge and skills in using digital technologies, where communication and access to information occurs through Internet platforms, social networks, and mobile devices are required.

The libraries of the future are more than just housing centers for books and media. They are invigorating meeting places and communities where truly meaningful learning and discovery takes place. As technology has transformed reading and learning, it has also transformed the vision of the library in both structure and function. Librarians have always been needed as guides and providers to assist in learning and discovery. Librarians in the information age play a critical role in access to and application of knowledge (Crockett, 2018). Librarians must be able to work with digital media, and must be able to curate electronic collections, including the ability to select, acquire, describe, organize, reference, and preserve these digital works. The role of librarians is continuing to evolve with the adoption of Internet and World Wide Web into the librarianship. Though it is difficult to predict with certainty how active the role of librarians would be in this evolving scenario, it can be said with confidence that their services cannot be dispensed with because they have the necessary qualification and historically the first right to

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attend to the information needs of the seekers (Joute, 2019).

Current pandemic is a real test of abilities, resources and services, the present situation demands that Librarians reach out to their users with information resources rather than serving them within the library's physical walls. Every crisis brings the opportunity to shape library services with modern and up-to-date digital technologies. In a way, social distancing and other barriers do not come between library digital resources and library users. In any disaster or pandemic, the need for knowledge and information requires that libraries and research-based institutions are fully equipped with digital technology (Ali, Naeem, & Bhatti, 2020). Some Librarians lack the requisite digital literacy skills to access the wealth of digital information resources available. Librarians must be empowered with all necessary digital literacy skills, embark on rigorous training and retraining programs, workshops, conferences and seminars, there should also be a coherent training policy for the Librarians on a sustainable basis to increase their requisite digital literacy skills (Abdulkadir, 2018).

However, today is the digital age wherein we are living in a world with Google Assistant, Siri, Alexa, and other digital information assistants, people have come to rely on technology to seek answers and find information. There is no exception for today's students. Twenty years ago, students might go to an encyclopedia for answers; now they can simply ask their smartphones or type the question into Google (Obinyan, 2020).

There were numerous studies on digital knowledge, skills and application but there are no studies yet conducted among the MUNPARLAS member schools and library staff. With the existing situation, the researcher has decided to conduct a study entitled Digital Knowledge, Skills and Application among Librarians and Library Staff of MUNPARLAS Library Association, Inc. to look deeper how literate and skilled the Librarians of MLAI are.

Theoretical / Conceptual Framework

This study considered Puentedura (2016) SAMR model that has four levels of integration (substitution, augmentation, modification, and redefinition) that provides a framework or template for educators to gauge their integration levels. As cited by Lacruz, (2018), SAMR model is a useful tool to reflect on classroom and institutional technological integration. The SAMR model was created to help in planning and assessing the levels of technologies used in the classroom. This model looks to aid teachers, administrators, and educators in examining the use of technology in the classroom (Ramzan, Asif, Ahmad, 2021). Although technology in and of itself cannot be the only guiding principle for curriculum development the SAMR model allows the educator to evaluate the level at which the students are using technology and "...becoming creators of their own knowledge" (Martzoukou, 2021). The model is encouraging that curriculum be created in a way that allows students to also learn the technological skills needed in the 21st century (Laar, Van Deursen, Van Dijk, & Haan, 2019).

The SAMR model is a tool for "assessing and evaluating technology practices and impacts in the classroom setting" and can be examined at both the student and teachers levels (Nnenda, & Nsirim, 2020). The SAMR model is a popular model to categorize learning activities within the levels of technological integration of substitution, augmentation, modification and redefinition. The model is a useful tool to reflect on an educators' integration of technology within their own classroom but can also be used by institutions to gauge the level of integration across the institution. Therefore, Puentedura (2016) SAMR model will be valuable in examining digital knowledge, skills and digital application of Librarians and library

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staff of MUNPARLAS Library Association, Inc.

Thus, theories provide a framework on which researches are built. They support and strengthen research and provide a basis of support on the topical issues studied. In this paper, electronic resources and digital library are discussed pointing out some of the resources that are needed for effective functioning of the digital library. The paper considered connectivity theory, self-efficacy theory, Wormell model, Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) in terms of the propounder of the theory, the year it was propounded and statement of the theory as well as their application to electronic resources and digital library environment. The paper suggests that, prospective researchers exploring the area of electronic resources and digital libraries can make use of these and other related theories to enrich their researches (Sawant & Yadav, 2020). Digital literacy certainly has the potential to contribute to far-reaching and important personal and societal consequences. Thus, increasing focus on development of digital literacy, however defined, should be a policy priority for all sectors (Julien, 2019). According to Kennan (2022) digital literacy skills are important because they enable access to information and engagement with government and support services that are increasingly provided online. This paper reviews literature and library programs world-wide to identify good practice in developing and facilitating digital literacy programs. Okeji, Tralagba and Obi (2020) study revealed the digital literacy skills that the librarians rated as very high and high, and those that they rated as moderate and low. The study also revealed the knowledge and competencies that they rated to be highly competent and competent, as well as also those that they rated to be neutral and not good.

Methods

Descriptive-correlational research design was used in this study. The study aimed to provide static pictures of situations as well as to establish the relationship between different variables. The respondents of this study were the Librarians and Library Personnel who are members of MUNPARLAS Library Association, Inc. that had a total number of 60. Based on the Raosoft calculator the recommended sample size was 53. Stratified sampling method was applied because of the three locations in MUNPARLAS (Muntinlupa, Parañaque and Las Piñas). The margin of error accepted was 5% while the level of confidence needed was 95%. The primary sources of data were the responses of the Librarians and library staff who are members of MUNPARLAS Library Association, Incorporated.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data. The results were presented in accordance to the statement of the problems.

Table 1

The Respondents' Level of Digital Knowledge

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Knowledge of software acquisition process (either through vendors or open-source platforms)	3.29	Very High	7

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2. Understand and use social media effectively	3.63	Very High	1
3. Knowledge of copyright laws in the digital environment.	3.42	Very High	4.5
4. Knowledge of digital preservation	3.25	Very high	8.5
5. Uploading documents to online platforms	3.50	Very High	3
6. Applying new technologies into library services	3.42	Very High	4.5
7. Use different storage devices to preserve digital contents (e.g., DVD, CD-ROM, etc.)	3.17	High	10
8. Ability to access open-source software	3.25	Very High	8.5
9. Create different file formats (PDF, GIF, bitmap, jpg)	3.54	Very High	2
10. Awareness of Search Engine Marketing (SEM)	3.38	Very High	6
Average	3.39	Very High	

Table 1 shows the level of digital knowledge among librarians and library staff of MUNPARLAS Library Association, Inc. Moreover, indicator 2 - Understand and use social media effectively has the highest weighted mean of 3.63 with verbal interpretation of very high. Followed by rank 2, indicator 9 - Create different file formats (PDF, GIF, bitmap, jpg) with weighted mean of 3.54, interpreted also as very high. Furthermore, the lowest rank in the respondents' level of digital knowledge is indicator 7 - Use different storage devices to preserve digital contents, e.g. DVD, CD-ROM, etc. with weighted mean of 3.17 described as high. The total average weighted mean is 3.39, therefore, the respondents' level of digital knowledge is very high.

Table 2

The Respondents' Level of Digital Skills

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Organizing electronic resources	3.12	High	10
2. Exchanging information with others on digital platforms using various strategies to collaborate, share, and communicate	3.27	Very High	4
3. Identify security measures and threats.	3.17	High	7.5
4. Marketing library services using social media.	3.37	Very High	2
5. Apply, evaluate, and manage information across digital and physical environments.	3.25	Very High	5
6. Evaluate suitability of software for digital projects	3.13	High	9

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7. Conduct a precise search in order to get focused information.	3.21	High	6
8. Engaging in digital spaces to design, create, and revise content online.	3.17	High	7.5
9. Can create and share digital content.	3.31	Very High	3
10. Can communicate and collaborate online.	3.50	Very High	1
Average	3.25	Very High	

Table 2 illustrates the level of digital skills among librarians and library staff of the MUNPARLAS Library Association, Inc. In the table indicator 10 ranked no.1 with weighted mean of 3.50 described as very high. This means that librarians and library staff have the skill to communicate and collaborate online. On the other hand, Indicator 4 ranked as no. 2 with a weighted mean of 3.37 described as very high. This indicates that librarians and library staff has a very high skill in marketing library services using social media. Moreover, indicator 2 gathered the lowest weighted mean of 3.12 and ranked no. 10 with verbal interpretation of high. This means that librarians and library staff need to develop more of their skills on the organization of electronic resources. Table 2 gathered 3.25 general weighted average mean described as very high. Therefore, MUNPARLAS librarians and staff possess a very high level of digital skills.

Table 3

The Respondents' Level of Digital Application

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Provide friendly interface to users.	3.56	Very High	3.5
2. Avail network facilities.	3.52	Very High	5.5
3. Support library functions.	3.67	Very High	1
4. Enhance advanced search, access and retrieval of information.	3.46	Very High	7.5
5. Improve the library operations.	3.60	Very High	2
6. Enable one to perform searches that is not practical manually.	3.46	Very High	7.5
7. Provide faster access to the holding of libraries worldwide through automated better catalogues	3.56	Very High	3.5
8. Digital technology affords multiple, simultaneous use from a single original which is not possible for materials stored in any other forms.	3.52	Very High	5.5
9. Cross references to other documents.	3.44	Very High	9.5
10. Eliminate time and space constraints	3.44	Very High	9.5
Average	3.52	Very High	

Table 3 illustrates the level of digital application among librarians and library staff of

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the MUNPARLAS Library Association, Inc. In the table, indicator 3-ranked no.1 with a weighted mean of 3.67 described as very high. This means that librarians and library staff have a very high level of digital application in terms of Support library functions. On the other hand, Indicator 5 ranked as no. 2 with a weighted mean of 3.6 described as very high. This indicates that librarians and library staff possess a very high level of digital applications in terms of improving the library operations. Moreover, indicator 9 & 10 gathered the lowest weighted mean of 3.44 and ranked 9.5 with verbal interpretation of very high. This means that librarians and library staff possess a very high level of digital applications in terms of cross references to other documents, eliminate time and space constraints. Table 3 gathered 3.52 general weighted average mean described as very high. Therefore, MUNPARLAS librarians and staff possess a very high level of digital applications.

Table 4

Overall Summary of the Levels of Digital Knowledge, Skills and Application Among Librarians and Library Staff of MUNPARLAS, Inc.

Respondents Level	Weighted Ave. Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
The Respondents' Level of Digital Knowledge	3.39	Very High	2
The Respondents' Level of Digital Skills	3.25	Very High	3
The Respondents' Level of Digital Application	3.52	Very High	1

Table 4 corresponds to the overall summary of the levels of digital knowledge, skills and applications among librarians and library staff of MUNPARLAS Library Association, Inc. In the summary, it shows that librarians and staff have a very high level of digital knowledge, skills and application in work.

Table 5

Relationship between the Respondents' Level of Digital Knowledge and Level of Digital Skill

	Pearson r	p-value	Interpretation
Respondents' Level of Digital Knowledge and Level of Digital Skills	0.812** High correlation	0.000	Significant
**Significant @ 0.01			

There is a significant relationship between the level of digital knowledge and the level of digital skills between librarians and library staff. Therefore, it means that the respondent's level of digital knowledge is lower than the level of digital skills.

Table 6

**Relationship between the Respondents' Level of Digital Skills
and Level of Digital Application**

	Pearson r	p-value	Interpretation
Respondents' Level of Digital Skills and Level of Digital Application	0.712** Moderate correlation	0.000	Significant
**Significant @ 0.01			

This means that there is significant relationship between the level of digital skills and the level of digital application among librarians and library staff. Which means that the level of digital skills is lower than the level of digital application.

Table 7

**Relationship between the Respondents' Level of Digital Knowledge
and Level of Digital Application**

	Pearson r	p-value	Interpretation
Respondents' Level of Digital Knowledge and Level of Digital Application	0.649**	0.000	Significant
	Moderate correlation		
**Significant @ 0.01			

There is significant relationship between the level of digital knowledge and the level of digital application among librarians and library staff. Therefore, it means that the level of digital knowledge is lower than the level of digital application.

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Table 8

Proposed Action Plan Based on the Results of the Study

Phase 1 Date: June 2023 Venue: Google Meet					
Objectives	Introduction		Resources Needed		Expected Output
	Strategic Activities	Participants	Human	Financial	
To provide awareness of result of the Digital Knowledge, Skills and Application among Librarians and Library Staff of MUNPARLAS Library Association, Incorporated.	Online Presentation of the result on the Digital Knowledge, Skills and Application among Librarians and Library Staff of MUNPARLAS Library Association, Incorporated.	Administrators, Librarians & Library Staff	Researcher	None	Awareness of the result of the case study
To set the day and time of the training or workshop.	Identify the day and time of the professional development training or workshop.	Administrators, Librarians & Library Staff	Researcher	None	Schedule of the training
To acquire consent to the MLAI officials to conduct training or workshop to the librarians and library staff.	Write a letter of permission to conduct training or workshop	Administrators, Librarians and library staff	MLAI Library Committee	None	Approval to conduct the workshop or training

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Phase 2					
Date: July 2023					
Venue: San Beda College Library - Alabang					
Objectives	Digital Knowledge		Resources Needed		Expected Output
	Strategic Activities	Participants	Human	Financial	
To enhance the professional competencies/capabilities of MLAI Librarians and library staff in terms of digital knowledge.	Webinar and online training on: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Knowledge of software acquisition process (either through vendors or open source platforms); b. Understand and use social media effectively; c. Knowledge of copyright laws in the digital environment; d. Knowledge of digital preservation; e. Uploading documents to online platforms; f. Applying new technologies into library services; g. Use different storage devices to preserve digital contents, e.g. DVD, CD-ROM, etc.; h. Ability to access open source soft wares; i. Create different formats (PDF, GIF, bitmap, jpg); and j. Awareness of Search Engine Marketing (SEM). 	Administrators, Librarians and library staff	Guest Lecturer	Training Fee	The librarian and library Staff can identify and apply digital knowledge at work. Assessment result after the training.

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Phase 3					
Date: August 2023					
Venue: Olivarez College Library					
Objectives	Digital Skills		Resources Needed		Expected Output
	Strategic Activities	Participants	Human	Financial	
To enhance the professional competencies/ capabilities of MLAI Librarians and library staff in terms of digital skills.	Webinar/Seminar, Training and benchmarking on: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Organizing electronic resources; b. Exchanging information with others on digital platforms using various strategies to collaborate, share, and communicate; c. Identify security measures and threats; d. Marketing library services using social media; e. Apply, evaluate, and manage information across digital and physical environments; f. Evaluate suitability of Software for digital projects; g. Conduct a precise search in order to get focused information; h. Engaging in digital spaces to design, create, and revise content online; i. Can create and share digital content; and j. Can communicate and collaborate online. 	Administrators, Librarians and library staff	Guest Lecturer	Training Fee	The librarian and library staff can identify and apply digital skills at work. Assessment result after the training.

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Phase 4 Date: September 2023 Venue: Southville International School and Colleges Library					
Objectives	Digital Application		Resources Needed		Expected Output
	Strategic Activities	Participants	Human	Financial	
To enhance the professional competencies/ capabilities of MLAI Librarians and library staff in terms of digital application.	Webinar/Seminar, Training and Benchmarking.	Administrators, Librarians and library staff	Guest Lecturer	Training Fee	The librarian and library Staff can identify and apply digital applications at work. Assessment result after the training.
Phase 5 Date: October 2023 Venue: PATTS College of Aeronautics Library					
Objectives	Culminating Activity		Resources Needed		Expected Output
	Strategic Activities	Participants	Human	Financial	
To provide rewards to the efforts made by the people who make the activity successful and meaningful.	Awarding of tokens and appreciation to the guest speakers, librarian and library staff who completed the trainings.	Administrators, Librarians and library staff	Guest Lecturer	Training Fee	The librarian and library staff can identify and apply digital KSA.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study revealed that the librarians and library staff demonstrated a very high level of digital knowledge, digital skills, and digital application. The results also demonstrated significant positive relationships between these three aspects, highlighting the interconnectedness of digital competencies in the library profession.

These findings emphasize the critical role of digital literacy within the realm of librarianship. In today's rapidly evolving information landscape, libraries and their staff must be well-equipped to harness digital tools and technologies to meet the changing needs of library users. MLAI should view these results as a call to action and continue to prioritize the development and maintenance of digital knowledge, skills, and application among its members. By doing so, MLAI can not only better serve its patrons but also position itself as a forward-

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thinking and adaptive organization in the digital age.

In light of these findings, it is recommended that MLAI consider implementing an action plan focused on ongoing digital training, skill enhancement programs, and the integration of digital technologies into library services. Such initiatives will not only benefit the individual members but also enhance the overall effectiveness and relevance of MLAI as a vital resource for its community.

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Цифрові знання, навички та застосування серед бібліотекарів та працівників бібліотек Бібліотечної асоціації MUNPARLAS

Мета. Дослідження мало на меті виявити та оцінити рівень цифрових знань, цифрових навичок та рівень застосування цифрових технологій бібліотекарями та працівниками бібліотек, які є членами Бібліотечної асоціації MUNPARLAS. **Методика.** У цьому дослідженні було використано описово-кореляційний дизайн дослідження, щоб надати статичну картину ситуацій, а також встановити взаємозв'язок між різними змінними. Респондентами цього дослідження стали 60 бібліотекарів та працівників бібліотек, які є членами Бібліотечної асоціації MUNPARLAS. **Результати.** Результати показали, що рівень цифрових знань респондентів дуже високий – середньозважений показник становить 3,39. Рівень цифрових навичок респондентів також був дуже високим – середньозважений показник склав 3,25. Крім того, рівень застосування цифрових технологій у респондентів був дуже високим – середньозважений показник склав 3,52. Існує значний зв'язок між цифровими знаннями та цифровими навичками респондентів, про що свідчить р-значення 0,000, що нижче за г-значення Пірсона 0,812. Аналогічно, існує значний зв'язок між цифровими навичками респондентів та цифровими додатками, що підтверджується значенням р-value 0,000, яке є нижчим за значення г-value Пірсона 0,712. Нарешті, між цифровими знаннями респондентів та цифровими додатками також спостерігався значний зв'язок: р-значення 0,000, що нижче за г-значення Пірсона 0,649. Таким чином, необхідно запропонувати план дій для підтримки цифрових знань, навичок і застосування серед бібліотекарів і працівників бібліотек в MLAI. **Висновки.** Результати цього дослідження підкреслюють важливість цифрової грамотності в бібліотечній справі. MLAI має й надалі надавати пріоритет розвитку цифрових знань, навичок і практичного застосування серед своїх співробітників, щоб адаптуватися до мінливих потреб користувачів і залишатися на крок попереду в цифрову епоху.

Ключові слова: цифрові знання; навички; бібліотекарі; бібліотечний персонал; бібліотечні асоціації

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